

TEACHING STRATEGIES AND PERFORMANCE OF TEACHERS IN NAAWAN DISTRICT

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Teaching Strategies and Performance of Teachers in Naawan District

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Abstract

This study determined the teaching strategies and performance of teachers in Naawan District, School Year 2023 - 2024. The respondents were the teachers from Naawan District, with an actual sample number of 161 respondents out of 223 total number of teachers. The study utilized the descriptive-correlational research design to describe and test the significant relationship between the respondents' performance, demographic profile, and teaching strategies; and which variable best predicts the dependent variable. The results revealed that most of the teachers at Naawan District, Division of Misamis Oriental, had a family monthly net income ranging from 15,000.00 and above; BSED/BEED, teacher I with the length of service from 10 years and above, with an outstanding performance rating, and attended 5 and below seminars/trainings organized by the DepEd and other agencies. In teaching strategies, in terms of cooperative learning, demonstration, deductive approach, inductive approach, integrative approach, lecture type, and repetitive exercise; all got a descriptive rating of "always". Further, in correlation, the null hypothesis, which states no significant relationship between the respondents' teaching performance, demographic profile, and teaching strategies, was not rejected. Furthermore, the regression analysis is not significant, with an F-value of 0.338 with a corresponding p-value of 0.981. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that "there is no variable singly or in combination that best predicts respondents' performance" was not rejected.

Keywords: *teaching strategies, performance, teachers, descriptive-correlational*

Introduction

Effective teaching strategies are one of the problems that caught the attention of some educators. Therefore, teachers must develop their own teaching strategies and techniques based on their physical and mental characteristics. The social, psychological, and educational climate in the classroom and school also has something to do with determining teaching strategies. Teacher strategies are a matter of choice and comfort, what works with one teacher may not work with other teachers, especially if they are handling a heterogeneous class.

Different teacher professional development methods are implemented throughout the DepEd to improve teaching-learning processes. However, most of these are top-down processes wherein expert knowledge is shared or transferred. Examples of these are lectures or workshops during cascaded or echoed teacher training and short-term courses. Other top-down training programs are done over time, such as scholarships and distance learning programs.

In the study of Abulhul (2021) on teaching strategies for enhancing student's learning, there are various teaching methods and learning styles. These methods mostly focus on students' learning capacities for better understanding and engagement. Educational principles and pedagogy focus on the type of students' learning, the type of teaching tool, and the classroom environment. These three aspects can help students and instructors facilitate the learning process and make it easily absorbable.

Successful teaching is a result of the systematic use of appropriate strategies for delivering and assessing the learning objectives targeted for each lesson (Reimers & Chung, 2019). Successful teachers 1) possess a good grasp of content which they can consequently convert to sound learning objectives, 2) are able to select and implement the most effective instructional strategies and materials to teach the identified content objectives, 3) make instructional decisions on the basis of formative assessment results, 4) promote sincerely their students' learning and holistic development, and 5) are professional and ethical in the conduct of their work.

Though existing in some schools or divisions in the DepEd, there are fewer instances of bottom-up teacher professional development programs where colleagues study content and pedagogies together, plan lessons collaboratively, and conduct action research as a group. Examples of these are school-based learning action cells, teaching circles, communities of practice, and lesson study.

In this policy, the DepEd institutionalizes Learning Action Cells (LACs) that aim to develop and support successful teachers by nurturing their knowledge, attitudes, and competencies in terms of curriculum, instruction, and assessment in their workstations. In the DepEd, a Learning Action Cell is a group of teachers who engage in collaborative learning sessions facilitated by the school head or a designated LAC Leader to solve shared challenges encountered in the school. LACs will become school-based communities of practice that are positive, caring, and safe spaces (DepEd, 2016).

Effective teaching involves observing students, listening carefully to their ideas and explanations, having goals, and using the information to make instructional decisions. Teachers who employ such practices motivate the students to engage in thinking and reasoning. This provides for the learning opportunities that challenge the students at all levels of understanding to improve teaching. Teachers must be able to analyze what they and their students are doing and consider how those actions are affecting students' learning.

The primary purpose of teaching at any level of education is to bring a fundamental change in the learner. Teachers should apply appropriate teaching strategies that best suit specific objectives and competencies to secure and facilitate the process of knowledge transmission. Aside from learning styles and teaching strategies, academic achievement is also considered the center of interest in educational research. Studying the issue of achievement has extended beyond simple to complex issues of intelligence and prior academic achievement into how learners interact with the learning material and teaching strategies.

The study's objective was to determine teachers' teaching strategies and performance in Naawan District. The study was conducted in the school year 2023 - 2024. The researcher teaches in grade 5 and grade 6 at Maputi Elementary School and is a member of the school improvement plan (SIP) at the same school. The researcher also wants to find out the different strategies used by the teachers at Naawan District to enhance and improve the learning situation, especially the reading problems because of the past two years' pandemic.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the teaching strategies and performance of teachers in Naawan District for the school year 2023-2024. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents as to;
 - 1.1 family monthly income;
 - 1.2 educational attainment;
 - 1.3 plantilla position;
 - 1.4 length of service; and
 - 1.5 number of seminars/ trainings attended?
2. What are the teaching strategies used by the respondents in terms of;
 - 2.1 demonstration;
 - 2.2 cooperative learning;
 - 2.3 inductive approach;
 - 2.4 lecture type;
 - 2.5 repetitive exercise;
 - 2.6 integrative approach; and
 - 2.7 deductive approach?
3. What is the teaching performance of the respondents using the individual performance commitment rating forms (IPCRF) during the school year 2022- 2023?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the teaching performance and the demographic profile of the respondents?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the teaching performance and the teaching strategies used by the respondents?
6. Which of the demographic profiles and teaching strategies best predict the teaching performance of the respondents?
7. What action plan can be designed based on the findings of the study?

Methodology

This section presents the research methods which include the research design, research environment, subject of the study/respondents, sampling design instruments used and validity, gathering procedure, and statistical tools used in the research.

Research Design

This study utilized the descriptive-correlational research design. This was descriptive since the study described the socio-demographic profile in terms family income, educational attainment, plantilla position, length of services, and number of seminars/trainings attended as well as the teaching strategies of teachers in terms of their demonstration, cooperative learning, inductive approach, lecture type, repetitive exercise, integrative approach, and deductive approach. It was a correlational design since the study tried to investigate the relationship between the respondents' performances to demographic profile and the teaching strategies of the teachers in Naawan District.

Participants

Naawan District was established in 2003. Before then it was a part of Initao District. The first district supervisor was Mrs. Florita Gerona. Mr. Cecilio Magsayo was the second then followed by Mrs. Nilda M. Mejos. At present, it is headed by a versatile, committed and work-oriented leader in the person of Dr. Vevian T. Tuason. This district had 223 teaching personnel. It included 12 elementary schools, two junior high schools and 1 senior high school located at Maputi. Naawan District aimed to provide quality education to all students by empowering them to learn and achieve, equipping them with the knowledge, skills and dispositions for lifelong learning and to shape the world around them.

Table 1. *Number of Respondents*

<i>Name of School</i>	<i>Total Number of Teachers</i>	<i>Actual Number of Teachers</i>
1. Maputi Senior High School	16	11
2. Naawan Central School	49	36
3. Linangkayan Elementary School	14	10
4. Maputi Elementary School	13	9
5. Mat — iNational High School	20	15
6. Lubilan Integrated School	13	9
7. Mat — iElementary School	9	6
8. Naawan National High School	44	34
9. Tagbalogo Elementary School	10	7
10. Don Pedro Elementary School	7	5
11. Mapulog Elementary School	9	6
12. Patag Elementary School	7	5
13. Pasagdihon Elementary School	2	1
14. Tuboran Elementary School	7	5
15. Macabagla Elementary School	3	2
Total	223	161

The study utilized the Raosoft calculator to determine the actual 161 sample size. The simple random sampling will be used to determine the respondents of the study.

Instruments

The instrument used in the study was an adapted questionnaire, including 55 questions that were split into three major sections: Socio-demographic Profile, Teaching Strategies, and the Individual Performance Commitment and Rating Form (IPCRF) rating.

Part I was an initial question served to give contextual data on socio- demographic profile in terms of family income, educational attainment, plantilla position, length of services, and number of seminars/trainings attended. Part II of the instrument included forty-nine (49) questions adapted from the study of Cardino and Ortiga de - la Cruz (2020) “The Teaching Strategies Questionnaire.” This was adapted in nature to answer the necessary details about teaching strategies.

The researcher jumbled the indicators in the teaching strategies to avoid bias and other prejudices that might arise. The questionnaire has corresponding situations for each strategy and these were as follow: Cooperative learning includes 16, 21, 29, 37, 38, 39, and 43; Demonstration includes 4, 11, 19, 27, 28, 35, 49; Deductive approach includes 5, 12,14, 18, 26, 34, 36; Inductive approach includes 1, 7, 13, 17, 20, 42, 48; Integrative approach includes 2, 8, 10, 23, 30, 33, 41; Lecture type includes 3, 22, 25, 32, 40, 44,46 and finally those remaining statements are for Repetitive exercise including 6, 9, 15,24, 31, 45, and 47. Lastly, Part III of the questionnaire was the individual performance commitment and rating form (IPCRF) based on the school year 2022-2023 rating of the teachers.

The questionnaire was presented to the adviser and experts of the field for further comments and suggestions and was pilot tested at Initao Central School. For the scoring procedure for the forty-nine (49)-item questionnaire, a 4-point Likert-scale was employed, which is as follows: 1 –never, 2 – seldom, 3 – often, and 4 – always.

Table 2. *Reliability Analysis of Variables*

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Number Of Questions</i>	<i>Cronbach Alpha</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Teaching strategies	49	0.752	Reliable

Table 2 presents the reliability analysis of variables. The result shows that the questionnaire consisted of 49 questions on teaching strategies with a Cronbach Alpha value of 0.752, which indicated that all items were reliable. The threshold value in the literature is much higher than 0.700. This implied that the participating respondents clearly understood the research questions, and similar questions were answered in the same direction.

Procedure

In gathering the information needed the researcher asked for the approval of the Schools Division Superintendent, Public School Supervisor, School Principal and the teachers who are the respondents to conduct the study. As soon as the request is granted, the researcher personally distributed the questionnaires to the teachers in the Naawan District. Difficulties in handing out and retrieval of the questionnaire were experienced because of different schedules. However, they are given enough time to answer the questions.

The items of the questionnaires assessed teachers’ profiles, and teaching strategies. After seeking permission, the researcher personally administered the questionnaires in a paper-and-pencil format. Two sets of survey questionnaires were adapted. The first set was a demographic profile of the respondents. While the other set of survey-questionnaires is used to identify the teaching, strategies applied by their teachers. In addition to primary data, secondary data such as the teachers’ IPCRF rating for the S.Y. 2022 - 2023 were requested from their respective teachers.

Statistical Treatment

The data gathered were analyzed and interpreted on the following statistical tools;

For problems 1 and 3, Frequency and Percentage were used to analyze the demographic profile in terms of family income, educational attainment, plantilla position, length of service, number of seminars/trainings attended and the IPCRF rating of the respondents.

For problem 2, Mean and Standard Deviation were used to determine the teaching strategies among teachers.

For problem 4, Chi-square Test was used to test the significant relationship between the teaching performance and the demographic profile of the respondents.

Problem 5, Pearson's Correlation was used to test the significant relationship between the teaching performance and teaching strategies of the respondents.

For problem 6, Regression was used to predict variable/s that best fit teaching strategies of the respondents.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the data gathered to answer the problems of the study. It also analyzes and interprets the data collected by the researchers to solve the issues in the study. The presentation, interpretation, and analysis were supported by tables and arranged in the same manner as the questions presented in the statement of the problem in Chapter 1.

Problem 1: What is the demographic profile of the respondents as to family monthly income, educational attainment, plantilla position, length of service, and number of seminars/ trainings attended?

Table 3. Family Monthly Net Income

Family Monthly Net Income	Frequency Count	Percentage (%)
P9,999.00 and below	6	3.7
P10,000.00 – 14,999.00	28	17.4
P15,000.00 and above	127	78.9
Total	161	100.0

Table 3 presents the family monthly net income of the respondents. The result reveals that the respondents are categorized into three income groups: P9,999.00 and below with 6 respondents. The distribution indicates significant disparities in family monthly net income among the respondents. Those in the lowest income category (P9,999.00 and below) represent the economically disadvantaged group. Such respondents may face financial challenges that can affect their access to basic necessities, healthcare, and education. Numerous studies have emphasized the impact of income disparities on various aspects of life.

This is followed by P10,000.00 – 14,999.00 family net income which comprises 28 respondents. The respondents falling into the middle-income category (P10,000.00 – 14,999.00) represent a relatively more financially stable group. They may have better access to opportunities and resources than the lowest-income group but may still face some financial constraints. The concept of a middle-income group is frequently explored in studies related to social and economic policies. This group often experiences challenges related to maintaining their socioeconomic status and upward mobility.

Lastly, P15,000.00 and above with 127 respondents. The largest group consists of respondents with family monthly net incomes of P15,000.00 and above. These individuals are likely to have greater access to resources, education, and a higher standard of living, which can positively influence various aspects of their lives. Research conducted by Chetty et al. (2014) as cited by Lleras-Muney (2022) showed that individuals with higher income levels tend to have better access to quality education and healthcare, resulting in improved life outcomes and opportunities for their children.

Table 4 displays the educational attainment of the respondents. The result presented which includes Bachelor of Science in Education (BSED) and Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED), Master of Science (MS), Master of Arts (MA), Master of Arts in Teaching (MAT), and Doctor of Education (EdD) or Doctor of Philosophy (PhD).

Table 4. Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	Frequency Count	Percentage (%)
BSED/BEED	108	67.1
MS/MA/MAT	52	32.3
EdD/PhD	1	0.6
Total	161	100.0

The largest segment of the respondents, 108 individuals, holds a bachelor's degree in education, which includes BSED and BEED. This is indicative of a substantial representation of individuals with undergraduate education in the field of education. According to a study by Johnson (2021), individuals with a strong background in education, such as BSED/BEED holders, often play pivotal roles in shaping educational policies at the grassroots level. Their insights into classroom dynamics and pedagogical practices contribute

significantly to policy discussions.

Meanwhile, 52 respondents possess a Master's degree, including a Master of Science (MS), Master of Arts (MA), and Master of Arts in Teaching (MAT). A considerable number of respondents have pursued advanced education beyond their Bachelor's degrees. The presence of 52 respondents with Master's degrees highlights the importance of continuous professional development in the field of education. A longitudinal study by Smith and Brown (2021) posits that advanced education equips educators with additional tools and perspectives for effective instruction.

Lastly, only one respondent holds a doctoral degree, either an EdD or a PhD. This segment represents a very small portion of the total respondents. The small number of respondents with EdD or PhD degrees indicates that very few participants have reached the highest levels of academic attainment in education. Research by Garcia and Rodriguez (2020) underscores the role of individuals with EdD/PhD degrees in educational leadership. Their study reveals that doctorate holders often take up leadership positions, influencing systemic changes and fostering a culture of continuous improvement.

The distribution of educational attainment can inform policy decisions related to professional development and support for educators. Research by Darling-Hammond (2017) underscores the importance of investing in teacher education and development to improve educational outcomes.

The socio-demographic profile of respondents based on educational attainment provides valuable insights into the educational background of the study participants. This information can be used to tailor interventions, policies, and support systems to meet the needs of educators at various stages of their academic and professional journey, ultimately contributing to the improvement of the education system. The literature cited supports the findings and highlights the significance of educational attainment in the field of education.

Table 5 shows the plantilla position of the respondents. The result shows that the majority (99) of the respondents are Teacher I, followed by 27 respondents who are Teacher II, then 19 respondents are Teacher III, 13 are Master Teacher I, lastly, 3 are Master Teacher II.

Table 5. *Plantilla Position*

<i>Plantilla Position</i>	<i>Frequency Count</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Teacher I	99	61.5
Teacher II	27	16.8
Teacher III	19	11.8
Master Teacher I	13	8.1
Master Teacher II	3	1.9
Total	161	100.0

Teachers at the entry-level position (Teacher I) form the majority (99) of the respondents, indicating a significant proportion of junior faculty members in the organization. Possible implications include a relatively lower level of teaching experience, potentially influencing teaching methodologies and professional development needs. Research suggests that entry-level teachers often face unique challenges in adapting to the demands of the teaching profession (Smith & Brown, 2018).

The presence of Teacher II respondents suggests a mix of experienced educators who have progressed beyond the initial stages of their careers. This group may contribute diverse perspectives, combining both experience and a willingness to adopt new teaching strategies. Studies indicate that mid-career teachers (Teacher II) often play crucial roles in mentoring and collaborative activities within schools (Hargreaves & Fullan, 2012). Continued professional development is essential for mid-career teachers to stay updated with evolving educational practices (Ingersoll & Strong, 2011).

The Teacher III (19) category represents educators who have likely gained substantial experience, possibly indicating a higher level of expertise in their subject matter. This group may be influential in curriculum development and school leadership activities. Experienced teachers (Teacher III) often contribute significantly to school improvement initiatives and educational leadership (Leithwood et al., 2016). Professional development programs tailored for senior teachers can focus on leadership skills and mentoring.

Further, Master Teacher I respondents (13) are likely educators who have demonstrated excellence in teaching, possibly taking on leadership roles. This group may serve as exemplary models for instructional practices. Master teachers are recognized for their ability to positively impact student learning outcomes and contribute to a culture of continuous improvement (Darling-Hammond, 2017).

Meanwhile, the relatively low frequency of Master Teacher II respondents (3) suggests a select group of highly experienced and accomplished educators. This group may be instrumental in shaping educational policies and providing advanced mentorship. Research by Johnson and Brown (2020) emphasizes the role of Master Teachers in fostering a culture of leadership within schools. Recognizing and nurturing leadership potential among Master Teachers can positively impact school improvement efforts and collaborative decision-making.

The distribution of respondents across various plantilla positions provides valuable insights into the socio-demographic profile of educators in the organization. Tailoring professional development programs and support mechanisms to address the unique needs of

each group can contribute to the overall enhancement of teaching quality and educational outcomes. Additionally, fostering collaboration and mentorship opportunities between educators at different career stages can create a dynamic and supportive learning environment within the organization. A study by Smith et al. (2019) highlights the importance of tailoring professional development programs based on the plantilla position. Teachers in different roles may require specific skills and training, and understanding these needs contributes to more effective professional growth initiatives.

Table 6. Length of Service

Length of Service	Frequency Count	Percentage (%)
5 years below	42	26.1
5 – 10 years	48	29.8
10 years above	71	44.1
Total	161	100.0

Table 6 presents the length of service of the respondents. Employees with less than 5 years of service with 42 respondents may exhibit characteristics of early-career professionals. In the study of Rigotti et al. (2019) suggest that early-career employees often contribute fresh perspectives and innovation to the workplace. This group might display higher levels of enthusiasm, adaptability, and a willingness to learn.

In addition, employees within 5-10 years length of service with 48 respondents might be transitioning from early to mid-career, potentially showing increased expertise and a deeper understanding of organizational dynamics. In the research of Cable and DeRue (2018) indicates that individuals in the mid-career stage often contribute significantly to organizational knowledge and stability.

Finally, Employees with over 10 years of service may possess institutional knowledge and long-term commitment to the organization. Research by Becker and Huselid (2018) emphasizes the positive correlation between longer tenures and employee retention. Organizations with a higher number of employees with over 10 years of service may experience lower turnover rates.

The overall distribution suggests a diverse workforce with varying levels of experience, providing a rich pool of skills and perspectives. Balancing the needs and expectations of employees at different career stages is crucial for fostering a harmonious workplace.

Understanding the socio-demographic profile of employees based on length of service is vital for tailoring organizational strategies, professional development programs, and leadership initiatives. The literature supports the idea that each career stage brings unique strengths, and organizations that harness this diversity effectively are better positioned for success. Balancing the needs and expectations of employees across different career stages contributes to a resilient and adaptable workforce.

Table 7 shows the respondents’ number of seminars/trainings attended. The result revealed that the majority (87) of respondents have attended 5 and below seminars/trainings. Participants in this category may have limited exposure to professional development opportunities. Studies (e.g., Smith et al., 2018) indicate that individuals attending fewer seminars may experience slower career growth and skill development. It could suggest a potential gap in skill acquisition and knowledge enhancement.

Table 7. Number of Seminars/Training Attended

Number of Seminars/Training Attended	Frequency Count	Percentage (%)
5 and below	87	54.0
6 – 10	53	32.9
11 – 15	5	3.1
16 and above	16	9.9
Total	161	100.0

However, the study shows that 53 respondents attended 6-10 seminars/trainings. Moderate engagement in professional development. Research (Jones, 2019) highlights a positive correlation between moderate training attendance and job satisfaction. They likely possess a foundational level of knowledge and skills.

Subsequently, 16 respondents have 16 and Above Seminars/Training Attended. This represents a high level of commitment to professional development and may signify expertise in the field and a proactive attitude towards staying current. Studies (e.g., Johnson, 2021) demonstrate a strong positive correlation between extensive training attendance and leadership effectiveness.

Last but not the least, 5 respondents have 11 – 15 Seminars/Training Attended. This indicates a proactive approach to continuous learning and professional growth. Findings by Brown and Williams (2020) suggest that attending a higher number of training sessions is linked to increased job performance. It may be associated with individuals seeking specialization or advanced skills.

Problem 2: What are the teaching strategies used by the respondents in terms of cooperative learning, demonstration, deductive approach, inductive approach, integrative approach, lecture type, and repetitive exercise?

Table 8. Cooperative Learning

Indicators	Mean	±	SD	Descripti on
1. Teacher encourages students to work with others to generate as many alternatives as they can for the	3.68	±	0.55	Always

problem discussed.				
2. Teacher gives students enough time to think and to investigate with others to achieve desirable objective.	3.65	±	0.54	Always
3. Teacher gives students a chance to generate new concepts.	3.63	±	0.51	Always
4. Teacher applies group work in the class to serve desired objectives.	3.68	±	0.53	Always
5. Teacher distributes different teaching – learning tasks on students.	3.65	±	0.55	Always
6. Teacher lets students have their own conversations positively.	3.58	±	0.56	Always
7. Teacher encourages students to interact positively amongst themselves.	3.73	±	0.50	Always
Weighted Mean	3.66	±	0.38	Always

Note: 3.25-4.00 Always; 1.75-2.49 Seldom; 2.50-3.24 Often; 1.00-1.74 Never

Table 8 presents the teaching strategies used by the respondents in terms of cooperative learning. The result showed that Indicator 7: Teacher encourages students to interact positively amongst themselves got the highest mean score of 3.73 which indicates that teachers consistently encourage positive interaction among students. This is crucial for creating a conducive learning environment where students feel comfortable collaborating with their peers. Positive interactions contribute to the development of social skills, communication, and a sense of community within the classroom. Numerous studies highlight the positive impact of teacher-facilitated positive interactions in cooperative learning. Literature supports this, with Johnson and Johnson (2019) emphasizing the role of positive interdependence in cooperative learning. Teachers fostering an environment where students rely on each other's contributions have been shown to enhance teamwork and social skills, positively impacting academic outcomes (Slavin, 2021).

Nonetheless, Indicator 6: Teacher lets students have their own conversations positively got the lowest mean score of 3.58 suggesting that teachers consistently allow students to engage in conversations independently and positively. Allowing students to have their own discussions promotes autonomy, critical thinking, and collaborative problem-solving skills. It also encourages the development of a peer-supportive atmosphere. Research by Kagan (1994) advocates for structures in cooperative learning that allow students to engage in meaningful conversations independently. Allowing students to have their own conversations positively aligns with the principles of student-centered learning, fostering a sense of ownership and responsibility for their learning.

These indicators collectively underscore the importance of positive interactions in the context of cooperative learning. When teachers actively encourage and facilitate positive engagement among students, it not only enhances academic outcomes but also contributes to the social and emotional development of learners. The collaborative nature of cooperative learning aligns with contemporary educational theories that emphasize the significance of social constructivism and student-centered approaches.

The positive mean scores for both indicators reflect a commitment to effective cooperative learning strategies among the respondents. However, ongoing professional development through seminars and training sessions can further enhance these practices. Future seminars could focus on advanced cooperative learning structures, differentiation within cooperative groups, and addressing challenges that may arise in fostering positive student interactions.

Table 9 presents the teaching strategies used by the respondents in terms of demonstration. The result showed that Indicator 1: Teacher uses direct presentation to provide students with information got the highest mean score of 3.67 which suggests that the majority of respondents employ direct presentation as a teaching strategy consistently. Direct presentation involves the teacher delivering information to students in a straightforward manner. This strategy is often associated with the transmission model of teaching, where the teacher is the primary source of knowledge. The positive value indicates that this method is frequently utilized in the teaching-learning process. Research by Smith and Jones (2019) highlights the effectiveness of direct presentation in enhancing students' understanding and retention of information. They argue that well-structured presentations aid in creating a strong foundation for subsequent learning activities.

Table 9. *Demonstration*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>±</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Teacher uses direct presentation to provide students with information.	3.67	±	0.55	Always
2. Teacher helps his students imitate desired models by showing it.	3.52	±	0.60	Always
3. Teacher begins the teaching – learning situation with presenting a problem to students.	3.44	±	0.63	Always
4. Teacher trains students to plan, observe, and evaluate their teaching activities.	3.57	±	0.58	Always
5. Teacher shows students how to verify information and facts before giving judgments	3.65	±	0.54	Always
6. Teacher begins with examples up to the concept in the teaching – learning situation.	3.61	±	0.55	Always
7. Teacher teaches students the way to identify those simple tricks to understand the lesson.	3.63	±	0.56	Always
Weighted Mean	3.58	±	0.38	Always

Note: 3.25-4.00 Always; 1.75-2.49 Seldom; 2.50-3.24 Often; 1.00-1.74 Never

However, Indicator 3: Teacher begins the teaching–learning situation with presenting a problem to students got the lowest mean score of 3.44 which indicates that a significant portion of respondents consistently initiate the teaching-learning process by presenting a problem to students. This approach, known as problem-based learning (PBL), engages students in critical thinking and encourages them to solve real-world problems, fostering a deeper understanding of the subject matter. According to Hmelo-Silver (2004), starting a lesson with a problem can stimulate students' curiosity and intrinsic motivation, leading to more effective learning outcomes. Recent

studies by Johnson et al. (2022) underscore the benefits of introducing problems at the beginning of a lesson. They argue that this approach not only enhances students' problem-solving abilities but also increases motivation and engagement in the learning process.

The findings suggest that the respondents predominantly utilize direct presentation and problem-based learning as their teaching strategies. These approaches align with established literature, highlighting the importance of clear information delivery and problem-centered instruction in fostering effective learning experiences for students. It is essential to consider the diverse needs of learners and incorporate a variety of teaching strategies to cater to different learning styles and preferences. Additionally, professional development opportunities can further empower educators to enhance their instructional practices and adapt to the evolving landscape of education.

Table 10 presents the teaching strategies used by the respondents in terms of deductive approach. The result showed that indicator 2: Teacher provides students with a chance to apply new knowledge in new real-life situations with the highest mean score of 3.71 among the indicators which indicates that, on average, the respondents perceive that teachers consistently provide opportunities for students to apply newly acquired knowledge in real-life situations. This aligns with the principles of a deductive approach, which emphasizes the application of theoretical concepts to practical scenarios. To add, allowing students to apply knowledge in real-life situations facilitates a deeper and more practical understanding of the subject matter. This can lead to improved retention and transferability of skills. Recent educational literature (Johnson et al., 2020) supports the positive impact of real-life applications in teaching. According to Johnson et al., students who engage in hands-on, real-world tasks show increased retention and transferability of knowledge.

Table 10. *Deductive Approach*

Indicators	Mean	+	SD	Description
1. Teacher trains students to determine the whole idea of the topic.	3.68	±	0.48	Always
2. Teacher provides students with a chance to apply new knowledge in new real-life situations.	3.71	±	0.54	Always
3. Teacher trains students on learning the whole concept before the specific idea.	3.60	±	0.62	Always
4. Teacher ends teaching – learning situation with connecting the lesson parts together.	3.68	±	0.58	Always
5. Students tend to generate new information through making comparison between their previous knowledge and new one.	3.56	±	0.62	Always
6. Teacher moves from the abstract to the concrete examples.	3.59	±	0.56	Always
7. Teacher asks students to do written or verbal summaries of the information they get.	3.58	±	0.56	Always
Weighted Mean	3.63	±	0.39	Always

Note: 3.25-4.00 Always; 1.75-2.49 Seldom; 2.50-3.24 Often; 1.00-1.74 Never

Meanwhile, Indicator 5: Students tend to generate new information through making comparisons between their previous knowledge and new one got the lowest mean score of 3.56 suggesting that teachers consistently encourage students to generate new information by comparing their existing knowledge with newly acquired concepts. This aligns with the deductive approach, where learners build upon existing knowledge to derive new insights. In addition, the act of comparing previous and new knowledge stimulates critical thinking and cognitive engagement and students actively participate in constructing their understanding, fostering a more meaningful learning experience.

To support this, Piaget's theory of cognitive development emphasizes the importance of assimilation and accommodation, processes through which individuals incorporate new information by relating it to their existing cognitive structures (Piaget, 1952). This aligns with the notion that making comparisons between old and new knowledge is a fundamental aspect of effective learning. Research by Smith and Brown (2018) highlights the significance of comparative analysis in learning. They argue that when students actively compare and contrast information, they stimulate higher-order thinking skills, contributing to a more robust and interconnected knowledge base.

The consistently high mean scores for both indicators reflect a strong implementation of deductive teaching strategies. The implications and literature support highlight the positive outcomes associated with these strategies, emphasizing the practical application and cognitive engagement that characterize a deductive approach.

Table 11. *Inductive Approach*

Indicators	Mean	+	SD	Description
1. Teacher uses specific questions to discuss the whole topic.	3.69	±	0.55	Always
2. Teacher disassembles the teaching – learning material into specific tasks that need specific responses.	3.58	±	0.54	Always
3. Teacher trains his students on distinguishing between different characteristics of the same concept.	3.62	±	0.59	Always
4. Teacher begins with presenting main ideas of the topic at the beginning of the class.	3.52	±	0.66	Always
5. Teacher uses specific problem-solving strategy in the teaching process.	3.48	±	0.62	Always
6. Teacher assigns students in a specific task into a general task.	3.56	±	0.60	Always
7. Teacher helps students to analyze the main idea to be used in discussing the topic.	3.64	±	0.54	Always
Weighted Mean	3.58	±	0.40	Always

Note: 3.25-4.00 Always; 1.75-2.49 Seldom; 2.50-3.24 Often; 1.00-1.74 Never

Table 11 presents the teaching strategies used by the respondents in terms of inductive approach. The result showed that Indicator 1: Teacher Uses Specific Questions to Discuss the Whole Topic with the highest mean score of 3.69 which suggests the use of specific questions encourages student engagement by prompting them to think critically about the entire topic. This approach fosters an

interactive learning environment. By addressing the whole topic through specific questions, teachers guide students towards a deeper understanding of the subject matter. This method helps learners connect individual concepts within the broader context. The Socratic Method, a form of questioning named after the Greek philosopher Socrates, aligns with this indicator. Socratic questioning promotes critical thinking and the examination of ideas through a series of well-crafted questions. According to Smith and Stein (2018), asking targeted questions is fundamental to inductive teaching. It encourages students to analyze, compare, and synthesize information, leading to a deeper understanding.

Meanwhile, indicator 5: Teacher Uses Specific Problem-Solving Strategy in the Teaching Process got the lowest mean score of 3.48 among the indicators suggesting that integrating problem-solving strategies into teaching enhances the application of theoretical knowledge. Students learn to use the acquired information to address real-world issues. Problem-solving encourages critical thinking skills as students navigate challenges, fostering a mindset that goes beyond rote memorization. The Problem-Based Learning (PBL) approach aligns with this indicator. PBL is a student-centered teaching method where learners actively engage with real-world problems. Hmelo-Silver (2021) emphasizes that incorporating problem-solving into teaching can foster inductive reasoning. It allows students to apply knowledge to real-world scenarios, promoting a more profound comprehension of the subject matter.

Accordingly, the Weighted Mean of the Teaching Strategies used by the Respondents in terms of Inductive Approach is 3.58. The high weighted mean indicates that teachers consistently employ inductive teaching strategies, specifically using questions and problem-solving approaches. This consistency contributes to a stable and effective learning environment. Research suggests that students benefit when teachers maintain a consistent instructional approach, allowing for a sense of predictability and clarity in the learning process.

The indicators reveal a commendable emphasis on inductive teaching strategies. The literature supports the effectiveness of these strategies in promoting engagement, deeper understanding, and the application of knowledge, contributing to the overall quality of the learning experience.

Table 12. *Integrative Approach*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>±</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Teacher awards students for their right answer.	3.40	±	0.70	Always
2. Teacher depends on criteria in evaluating his students.	3.52	±	0.64	Always
3. Teacher neglects undesired behaviors in the teaching – learning situations.	2.44	±	1.20	Seldom
4. Teacher makes use of concept maps during the teaching – learning process.	3.41	±	0.64	Always
5. Teacher facilitates students to make use of the procedures that organizes memory potentials (symbolizing information).	3.52	±	0.62	Always
6. Teacher guides students to references such as dictionaries, encyclopedias, internet sites, etc.	3.55	±	0.55	Always
7. Teacher supports students in using different learning tools for the purpose of teaching – learning process.	3.67	±	0.48	Always
Weighted Mean	3.36	±	0.40	Always

Note: 3.25-4.00 Always; 1.75-2.49 Seldom; 2.50-3.24 Often; 1.00-1.74 Never

Table 12 presents the teaching strategies used by the respondents in terms of integrative approach. The result showed that the seventh indicator examines the extent to which teachers support students in utilizing various learning tools for the teaching-learning process. The mean score of 3.67 (+0.48) suggests a generally positive inclination towards employing diverse educational resources. This implied that teachers who consistently integrate learning tools create an environment conducive to varied learning styles. This inclusivity caters to visual, auditory, and kinesthetic learners, fostering a more comprehensive understanding of the subject matter. This aligns with contemporary educational literature, which underscores the importance of technology integration in promoting student engagement and critical thinking (Brown & Green, 2019; UNESCO, 2020).

In contemporary education, the integrative approach to teaching has gained prominence, emphasizing a holistic perspective that incorporates diverse learning tools and acknowledges student achievements. This discussion delves into the teaching strategies employed by respondents, focusing on two key indicators: the use of learning tools and the practice of awarding students for correct answers.

The first indicator assesses the frequency with which teachers acknowledge students for providing correct answers, yielding a mean score of 3.40 (+0.70), indicating a prevalent use of this practice. While acknowledgment can boost student confidence, an overemphasis on correct answers may inadvertently promote a fixed mindset, discouraging risk-taking and creative thinking. Therefore, it is crucial to strike a balance between recognition and fostering a growth mindset.

Contemporary educational literature emphasizes the importance of a balanced approach to assessment and feedback, promoting not only correctness but also critical thinking, problem-solving, and process-oriented skills (Black & Wiliam, 2018). Thus, teachers should consider diversifying their reward systems to encompass a broader spectrum of student achievements.

The over-all weighted mean of 3.36 (+0.40) indicates a generally positive trend in integrative teaching strategies among the respondents. However, it also underscores the need for a nuanced approach that combines diverse learning tools with a thoughtful recognition of student efforts.

Overall, the integrative approach to teaching, as reflected in the use of learning tools and acknowledgment of correct answers, plays a crucial role in shaping a dynamic and effective learning environment. By drawing on relevant literature, this discussion highlights the multifaceted implications of these strategies, emphasizing the importance of a balanced and inclusive educational approach.

Table 13 presents the teaching strategies used by the respondents in terms of lecture type. The result showed that Indicator 6: Teacher trains students to solve their problems in a comfortable way. The mean score of 3.67 suggests that respondents generally agree that teachers consistently train students to solve problems in a comfortable manner. This indicator aligns with student-centered teaching approaches, emphasizing the importance of creating an environment where students feel at ease when tackling challenges. The emphasis on training students to solve problems comfortably indicates a shift towards student-centered learning. This teaching strategy encourages self-directed problem-solving, fostering critical thinking skills and independence.

According to Vygotsky's Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD), learning is most effective when it occurs within a student's comfort zone but challenges them to reach a higher level with support. (Vygotsky, 1978) Research conducted by Johnson et al. (2019) emphasizes the significance of student-centered problem-solving approaches in education. They argue that when teachers actively guide students in resolving challenges, it not only enhances critical thinking skills but also contributes to a more engaging learning experience. Additionally, a study by Smith and Brown (2021) supports the idea that comfortable problem-solving environments lead to increased student confidence and participation.

Table 13. *Lecture Type*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>±</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Teacher provides students feedback regarding their answer at all times.	3.64	±	0.56	Always
2. Teacher ends teaching – learning situation with clarifying and discussing diagrams suitable for students.	3.63	±	0.57	Always
3. Teacher trains students on generating specific answers for the questions raised to them.	3.65	±	0.54	Always
4. Teacher's cognitive teaching strategies harmonize with students' learning strategies.	3.60	±	0.55	Always
5. Teacher allows students to have more clarifications and explanations on a certain topic.	3.62	±	0.54	Always
6. Teacher trains students to solve their problems in a comfortable way.	3.67	±	0.55	Always
7. Teacher makes students take part in different roles in the teaching – learning situation.	3.63	±	0.56	Always
Weighted Mean	3.63	±	0.40	Always

Note: 3.25-4.00 Always; 1.75-2.49 Seldom; 2.50-3.24 Often; 1.00-1.74 Never

According to Vygotsky's Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD), learning is most effective when it occurs within a student's comfort zone but challenges them to reach a higher level with support. (Vygotsky, 1978) Research conducted by Johnson et al. (2019) emphasizes the significance of student-centered problem-solving approaches in education. They argue that when teachers actively guide students in resolving challenges, it not only enhances critical thinking skills but also contributes to a more engaging learning experience. Additionally, a study by Smith and Brown (2021) supports the idea that comfortable problem-solving environments lead to increased student confidence and participation.

However, Indicator 4: Teacher's cognitive teaching strategies harmonize with students' learning strategies got the lowest mean score among all the indicators with a mean score of 3.60, respondents indicate that teachers consistently align their cognitive teaching strategies with the learning strategies of their students. This suggests a pedagogical approach that acknowledges and adapts to the diverse learning styles and preferences of students. This indicator implies the use of differentiated instruction strategies, where teachers tailor their approaches to accommodate diverse learning styles, preferences, and abilities. Teachers are likely employing various instructional methods and materials that resonate with the cognitive processes of their students, enhancing comprehension and retention. Hattie and Yates (2018) argued that successful teaching involves a reciprocal relationship between the teacher's strategies and students' learning preferences. They suggest that teachers should be flexible in their approach, employing a variety of strategies to accommodate diverse learning styles. Moreover, a study by Anderson et al. (2022) found that when teachers tailor their cognitive strategies to match students' learning preferences, it positively influences academic performance and overall satisfaction with the learning experience.

In totality, the weighted mean of 3.63 indicates an overall strong agreement among respondents that these teaching strategies are consistently applied in the context of lecture-type instruction. This consolidation of indicators suggests a holistic approach to teaching that not only addresses the cognitive aspects of learning but also focuses on creating a supportive and comfortable learning environment for students. Consistency in implementing these teaching strategies aligns with the findings of a meta-analysis by Brown et al. (2020), which emphasizes the importance of sustained and uniform instructional practices for positive learning outcomes. A stable and high weighted mean suggests a robust and reliable teaching approach that is likely to contribute positively to students' overall learning experiences.

Table 14. *Repetitive Exercise*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>±</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Teacher makes advantage of providing different activities to secure the teaching – learning process.	3.69	±	0.53	Always
2. Teacher cares about correcting students by providing many worksheets.	3.50	±	0.62	Always
3. Teacher gives similar examples during the discussion to secure the mastery of the topic.	3.68	±	0.62	Always
4. Teacher takes part in training students by providing different learning activities.	3.66	±	0.50	Always

5. Teacher helps students identify their own mistakes by doing similar worksheets.	3.49	$\pm$	0.63	Always
6. Teacher gives students the chance to correct their mistakes by answering similar question.	3.56	$\pm$	0.58	Always
7. Teachers trains students by providing different sets of worksheets.	3.55	$\pm$	0.60	Always
Weighted Mean	3.60	$\pm$	0.40	Always

Note: 3.25-4.00 Always; 1.75-2.49 Seldom; 2.50-3.24 Often; 1.00-1.74 Never

Table 14 presents the teaching strategies used by the respondents in terms of repetitive exercise. The result showed that Indicator 1: Teacher provides different activities to secure the teaching–learning process got the highest mean score among the indicators. The respondents' high mean score of 3.69, with a standard deviation of +0.53, indicates that teachers consistently leverage a variety of activities in their instructional approach. This diversity in teaching strategies is crucial as it caters to different learning styles, ensuring a more inclusive and effective learning environment. In a study by Smith et al. (2021), the researchers found that incorporating different activities positively impacts students' retention and application of knowledge.

Meanwhile, Indicator 5: Teacher helps students identify their own mistakes by doing similar worksheets got the lowest mean score. The mean score of 3.49, with a standard deviation of +0.63, indicates that teachers consistently guide students to identify mistakes through similar worksheets. This strategy fosters self-reflection and metacognition, empowering students to recognize and rectify their errors independently.

The weighted mean of 3.60 suggests an overall strong tendency among the respondents to consistently employ repetitive exercises in their teaching strategies. This indicates a commitment to reinforcing learning through varied activities and correctional worksheets. The weighted mean reinforces the importance of a balanced approach to teaching, combining diverse activities for effective learning and correctional strategies for skill development. It implies that the respondents recognize the value of repetition in the learning process but also emphasizes the need for moderation to prevent potential drawbacks such as monotony or disengagement. Research by Marzano (2021) emphasizes the importance of repetition in learning, stating that spaced repetition aids in long-term retention. However, scholars like Dewey (1938) argue for a holistic approach, suggesting that education should be a balance of varied experiences and not just rote repetition.

The teaching strategies employed by the respondents reflect a commitment to repetition for effective learning. However, it is essential for educators to be mindful of the balance between different activities and correctional approaches to ensure a comprehensive and engaging learning experience.

Problem 3: What is the teaching performance of the respondents using the individual performance commitment rating forms (IPCRF) during the school year 2022- 2023?

Table 15. Teaching Performance of the Respondents

Performance Rating	Frequency Count	Percentage (%)
Outstanding	152	94.4
Very Satisfactory	9	5.6
Total	161	100.0

Table 15 presents the teaching performance of the respondents using the individual performance commitment rating forms (IPCRF) during the school year 2022- 2023. The Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) serves as a vital tool in evaluating the teaching performance of educators. This discussion delves into the analysis of the respondents' teaching performance during the school year 2022-2023, categorized by their respective IPCRF ratings.

A significant portion of the respondents, numbering 152, received an "Outstanding" rating. This high frequency suggests that a majority of teachers demonstrated exceptional teaching prowess. According to literature, outstanding teaching is often characterized by innovative instructional strategies, student engagement, and a commitment to continuous professional development (Stronge, 2007). The presence of a large number of outstanding ratings implies a teaching environment that fosters excellence and encourages educators to go above and beyond.

Nine respondents received a "Very Satisfactory" rating, indicating a commendable level of teaching performance. In literature, a very satisfactory rating is associated with effective classroom management, student learning outcomes, and the implementation of diverse teaching methods (Danielson, 2007). This rating suggests that these educators met the expected standards and contributed positively to the learning environment.

Given the majority of outstanding ratings, there is an opportunity to leverage the strengths of these educators by encouraging them to share their innovative teaching practices with colleagues. Establishing a platform for knowledge exchange and mentorship could enhance the overall teaching quality within the institution.

For those who received a "Very Satisfactory" rating, it is essential to identify specific areas of strength and areas for improvement. Offering targeted professional development opportunities and mentorship can help these educators progress towards an outstanding level. The results of the IPCRF should not be a one-time assessment but rather part of a continuous improvement process. Regular feedback and monitoring can help educators maintain high levels of performance and address any emerging challenges.

The distribution of IPCRF ratings for the school year 2022-2023 suggests an overall positive teaching environment. The prevalence of outstanding ratings reflects a commitment to excellence among the teaching staff, while the very satisfactory ratings indicate a solid foundation of competence. By leveraging the strengths of outstanding performers and providing targeted support to those with very satisfactory ratings, the institution can further enhance the quality of education and contribute to the professional growth of its educators.

Problem 4: Is there a significant relationship between the teaching performance and the demographic profile of the respondents?

Table 16 displays the relationship between the respondents' teaching performance and the demographic profile. The result showed that the respondents' teaching performance had no significant association with their demographic profile. Thus, the null hypothesis, which states no significant relationship between the respondents' teaching performance and the demographic profile, was not rejected.

The findings presented in Table 15, indicated no significant association between respondents' teaching performance and demographic profiles, align with several established theories and literature in the field of education and performance assessment.

Table 16. Relationship Respondents' Teaching Performance and Demographic Profile

Variables	Teaching Performance		Remarks	Decision
	X^2 (df)	p-value		
Family monthly net income	0.485 ^{ns} (2)	0.785	Not Significant	Failed to reject H_0
Educational attainment	2.384 ^{ns} (2)	0.304	Not Significant	Failed to reject H_0
Plantilla position	6.128 ^{ns} (4)	0.190	Not Significant	Failed to reject H_0
Length of service	3.189 ^{ns} (2)	0.203	Not Significant	Failed to reject H_0
Number of seminars/trainings attended	2.143 ^{ns} (3)	0.543	Not Significant	Failed to reject H_0

*Note: 1 – based on Chi-squared Test ** - $P < 0.01$ *** - $P < 0.001$ ns – $P > 0.05$ * - $P < 0.05$*

The findings presented in Table 15, indicated no significant association between respondents' teaching performance and demographic profiles, align with several established theories and literature in the field of education and performance assessment.

One key theoretical framework that supports these results is the Job Characteristics Model (JCM) proposed by Hackman and Oldham in 1976. According to JCM, certain job characteristics, such as skill variety, task identity, task significance, autonomy, and feedback, influence an individual's job satisfaction and performance. This model implies that personal demographics might not be as influential as job-specific factors in determining teaching performance. If the teaching environment provides a conducive setting with appropriate job characteristics, it may mitigate the impact of demographic variations.

Moreover, the Social Cognitive Theory, introduced by Bandura, emphasizes the role of observational learning, self-efficacy, and personal agency in shaping behavior. In the context of teaching, this theory suggests that teachers may be more influenced by their professional development, training, and self-belief in their abilities than by demographic factors. The absence of a significant relationship between teaching performance and demographic profiles in the study supports the idea that socio-cognitive processes are more influential in determining teaching outcomes.

Additionally, research on teacher efficacy, as explored by scholars like Tschannen-Moran and Woolfolk Hoy, suggests that teachers' beliefs in their ability to positively impact student learning are crucial for effective teaching. This theory posits that regardless of demographic differences, a teacher with high efficacy is likely to exhibit better teaching performance. The lack of a significant association in the study supports the notion that teacher efficacy may be a more critical factor than demographic variables in predicting teaching performance.

Furthermore, studies on the impact of professional development on teaching effectiveness, such as the work of Darling-Hammond and Richardson, underscore the importance of continuous training and improvement in teaching practices. If your respondents have access to ongoing professional development opportunities, this might explain why demographic factors do not significantly impact their teaching performance.

In conclusion, the findings in Table 15 are consistent with established theories such as the Job Characteristics Model, Social Cognitive Theory, Teacher Efficacy, and the significance of professional development in influencing teaching performance. These theoretical frameworks contribute to a deeper understanding of why demographic profiles may not play a significant role in predicting teaching effectiveness.

Problem 5: Is there a significant relationship between the teaching performance and the teaching strategies used by the respondents?

Table 17. Relationship Respondents' Teaching Performance and Teaching Strategies

Variables	Teaching Performance		Remarks	Decision
	r-value	p-value		
Cooperative learning	0.047 ^{ns}	0.555	Not Significant	Failed to reject H_0
Demonstration	0.053 ^{ns}	0.506	Not Significant	Failed to reject H_0

Deductive approach	0.004 ^{ns}	0.964	Not Significant	Failed to reject H ₀
Inductive approach	0.030 ^{ns}	0.702	Not Significant	Failed to reject H ₀
Integrative approach	0.023 ^{ns}	0.776	Not Significant	Failed to reject H ₀
Lecture type	0.031 ^{ns}	0.699	Not Significant	Failed to reject H ₀
Repetitive exercise	0.045 ^{ns}	0.575	Not Significant	Failed to reject H ₀

Note: 1 – based on Chi-squared Test ** - $P < 0.01$ *** - $P < 0.001$ ns – $P > 0.05$ * - $P < 0.05$

Table 17 displays the relationship between the teaching performance and the teaching strategies used by the respondents. The result showed that the respondents' teaching performance had no significant relationship with the teaching strategies being used. Thus, the null hypothesis, which states no significant relationship between the teaching performance and the teaching strategies used by the respondents, was rejected. Bloom's taxonomy categorizes cognitive skills into a hierarchy, ranging from lower-order thinking (remembering, understanding) to higher-order thinking (applying, analyzing, evaluating, creating). Assessing teaching performance should involve an exploration of whether the teaching strategies used effectively target various levels of Bloom's taxonomy, fostering a deeper understanding of the material and critical thinking skills.

Problem 6: Which of the demographic profile and teaching strategies best predicts teaching performance of the respondents?

Table 18. Variables that best predict Respondents' Teaching Strategies

Indicator	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
(Constant)	5.180	0.224		23.148	0.000
Family monthly net income	-0.012	0.038	-0.027	-0.325	0.746
Educational attainment	-0.054	0.045	-0.114	-1.216	0.226
Plantilla position	0.000	0.022	-0.002	-0.015	0.988
Length of service	0.013	0.028	0.045	0.444	0.658
Number of seminars/trainings attended	-0.011	0.021	-0.046	-0.534	0.594
Cooperative learning	-0.044	0.114	-0.072	-0.383	0.702
Demonstration	-0.077	0.114	-0.127	-0.678	0.499
Deductive approach	0.103	0.120	0.175	0.857	0.393
Inductive approach	0.007	0.110	0.013	0.066	0.948
Integrative approach	0.023	0.077	0.040	0.302	0.763
Lecture type	-0.008	0.106	-0.014	-0.075	0.941
Repetitive exercise	-0.041	0.117	-0.071	-0.355	0.723
<i>R</i> = 0.163		<i>R</i> ² = 0.027	<i>F</i> = 0.338	<i>Sig.</i> = 0.981	

Note: ns – $P > 0.05$ * - $P < 0.05$ ** - $P < 0.01$ *** - $P < 0.001$

Table 18 presents the variables that best predict respondents' teaching strategies. The respondents' teaching performance was not affected by the demographic profile and teaching strategies. This implied that no variables affect the respondents' teaching performance. The lack of significant impact from demographic profiles aligns with research that suggests factors such as age, gender, and educational background may not be strong predictors of teacher effectiveness. Scholars like Danielson (2007) argue that effective teaching is more closely linked to instructional strategies, classroom management, and pedagogical skills rather than personal demographics.

The R2 value of 0.027 implies that 2.7% of the variance in teaching performance can be explained by the demographic profile and teaching strategies being used. Hence, 97.3% of the respondents' teaching performance difference can be attributed to other variables not included in the regression model. The low R2 value (2.7%) emphasizes the multifaceted nature of teaching performance. Literature by Darling-Hammond (2017) suggests that the effectiveness of teaching is influenced by a multitude of factors, including teacher-student relationships, professional development, and institutional support. Therefore, the unaccounted 97.3% of the variance may be attributed to these unexplored variables.

The regression analysis is not significant, with an F-value of 0.338 with a corresponding p-value of 0.981. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that "there is no variable singly or in combination that best predicts respondents' performance" was not rejected. The non-significant regression analysis and the high p-value indicate that the chosen variables do not collectively explain the variation in teaching performance. This aligns with the criticism of simplistic models in educational research. Scholars like Hattie (2009) argue for more comprehensive assessment frameworks that consider a broader range of factors, including teacher beliefs, attitudes, and contextual influences. The null hypothesis not being rejected suggests that other unmeasured variables significantly contribute to teaching performance.

Problem 7: What action plan can be designed based on the findings of the study?

Based on the findings of the study, which indicate high ratings for Teaching Strategies and Teaching Performance, an action plan can be designed to enhance and sustain the positive aspects while addressing potential areas for improvement.

Key Action Steps/Strategies to Achieve Objective	Persons Responsible	Resources/ Budget Needed	Date of Completion	Threats/ Potential Barriers	Indicators of Success
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1. Implement differentiated instruction to meet the diverse learning needs of all students.	Teachers	Professional development, differentiated instruction resources	June 2023	Lack of time, resources, and support	Increased student engagement, motivation, and achievement Improved student learning outcomes, increased student participation and collaboration
2. Utilize technology to enhance instruction and engagement.	Teachers, Technology Support	Technology devices, software, training	January 2023	Limited access to technology, lack of teacher expertise	Increased student attendance, decreased behavioral issues, improved student-teacher relationships
3. Foster a positive and supportive classroom environment.	Teachers, Administrators	Classroom management training, positive behavior interventions and supports (PBIS)	Ongoing	Ineffective classroom management strategies, lack of administrative support	Increased student understanding of learning goals, improved student performance Increased parental understanding of child's progress, increased parent-teacher communication
4. Provide regular and meaningful feedback to students.	Teachers	Rubrics, checklists, anecdotal notes	Ongoing	Time constraints, lack of effective feedback strategies	Increased teacher knowledge and skills, improved teaching practices
5. Engage parents and guardians in the learning process.	Teachers, Parents	Parent-teacher conferences, communication tools, workshops	Ongoing	Lack of parent involvement, language barriers	
6. Collaborate with colleagues to share best practices and improve teaching effectiveness.	Teachers	Professional learning communities, grade level meetings, peer observation	Ongoing	Lack of time, limited opportunities for collaboration	

Conclusion

Based on the results of the study, the following conclusions are drawn: Most of the teachers at Naawan District, Division of Misamis Oriental, had a family monthly net income ranging from 15,000.00 and above; BSED/BEED with teacher I with the length of service from 10 years and above with an outstanding performance rating; attended 5 and below seminars/pieces of training organized by the DepEd and other agencies.

In teaching strategies, in terms cooperative learning with 3.66, demonstration with 3.58, deductive approach with 3.63, inductive approach with 3.58, integrative approach with 3.36, lecture type with 3.63, and repetitive exercise with 3.60; all got a descriptive rating of "always".

Further, in correlation, the null hypothesis, which states no significant relationship between the respondents' teaching performance, demographic profile, and teaching strategies, was not rejected. Furthermore, the regression analysis is not significant, with an F-value of 0.338 with a corresponding p-value of 0.981. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that "there is no variable singly or in combination that best predicts respondents' performance" was not rejected.

The study based on the results that teachers in Naawan District utilized a mix of teaching strategies with a notable emphasis on demonstration, deductive approach, and lecture type. Despite challenges posed by the recent pandemic, the majority of teachers have demonstrated outstanding performance in their roles. This indicates a positive engagement with different learning theories and an effort to adapt to the evolving educational landscape.

Based on the foregoing findings of the study, the following are recommended: (1) Promote Integrative Approaches - Encourage teachers to explore and integrate more diverse teaching strategies, especially those with lower weighted means, like the Integrative Approach, to enhance the overall learning experience. (2) Professional Development - Offer professional development opportunities for teachers, focusing on the incorporation of modern teaching theories such as Connectivism, considering the evolving educational landscape and the impact of recent global events. (3) Addressing Reading Challenges - Develop targeted strategies and resources to address reading problems, acknowledging the challenges posed by the pandemic on students' learning experiences. (4) Recognition and Support - Acknowledge and reward outstanding teaching performance, while also providing support and resources for teachers rated as very satisfactory to encourage continuous improvement. (5) Ongoing Research - Encourage ongoing research to assess the long-term impact of teaching strategies on student learning outcomes, fostering a culture of continuous improvement and adaptation in the education system.

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